

Millets : An Ancient Dietary Treasure Promoting Human Well-Being

Geetika Kalita and Highland Kayang

Centre for Advance Studies in Botany,
North-Eastern Hill University

Corresponding E-mail : mailmegeetikakalita@gmail.com

Millets, the oldest crop known for their small-seeded grains and belonging to the Poaceae family, offer immense nutritional benefits for human health. They hold a significant place in the traditional diets of various regions globally. With attributes such as high yield, nutritional density, drought resistance, and natural resistance to pests, millets are favored by inhabitants of arid regions across temperate, sub-tropical, and tropical climates with limited rainfall. Serving as both human food and livestock fodder, millets are hailed for their richness in proteins, micronutrients, and phytochemicals, exhibiting promising health-promoting properties including anti-diabetic, anti-obesity, and cardiovascular disease prevention effects. Due to these remarkable characteristics, millets are often referred to as “Miracle crops” and heralded as “Crops for the Future.”

Keywords: Millets, Oldest crop, Nutritional benefits.